

EVALUATION OF “NAGA AKONG GARBO” (NAGA) PROGRAMME: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND SUCCESSES

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Abstract:

This study evaluated the implementation of the “*Naga Akong Garbo*” (NAGa) Programme from its two components on (1) cleanliness, sanitation and health, and (2) governance systems and structures. It focused on the present status, challenges and successes experienced and achieved during the Programme implementation. Descriptive survey research design was employed and descriptive statistics were used in the data analysis. Findings revealed that the 20 purposively chosen key informants (KIs) consistently rated each indicator on cleanliness, sanitation, health and governance as implemented enough whereas governance structures was viewed as highly implemented. Programme implementation encountered challenges included highly technical indicators of the scorecards where progress and monitoring reporting become difficult and tedious. Some village officials were found to be unresponsive and non-cooperative because of differing political party affiliations and conflicting vested interests. A major challenge was the delayed releases funds causing subsequent delays of programme implementation. On the positive note, major successes have been achieved along improved public service delivery. Finally, the NAGa Programme provided avenues for the strengthened working relationships among various departments, stakeholders and the local people. It was very instrumental in the achieved successes on cleanliness, sanitation, health and governance systems of the city, more evidently along governance structures.

Keywords: Naga Akong Garbo (NAGa), cleanliness, sanitation, health, governance systems, governance structures, balance-scorecard, new public services theory

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1. Introduction

The City of Naga, Cebu in central Philippines, is one of the first class cities of Cebu province comprised of 28 villages founded on 12 June 1829. Naga is the oldest town of Cebu province before it was converted to the city status in 2007.

Naga city's guiding vision is to develop and uplift the standard of living of its constituents. The city government commits provide the effective and efficient delivery of basic government services for the welfare (Inabangan, Garcia and Abocejo, 2019), well-being and contentment of its constituency (Gilsing, 2013). Among the priorities of Naga City, under the leadership of its incumbent elected Mayor, is to put premium on "*Vision and Leadership 2020*", dubbed as VAL 2020 Programme which aims to nurture local economic growth (Abocejo et al., 2012), tourism (Abocejo, 2015a), education (Abocejo and Padua, 2010), heritage and cultural activities of the City (City of Naga, 2015). In response to VAL 2020, the "*Naga Akong Garbo*" (NAGa) Programme was launched and initiated to deliver more effective and efficient public services with the goal of creating inclusive, competitive and a liveable city. Originally, the NAGa Programme is a subproject of "*Our Cebu Programme*" whose long term goal is for sustainable development of the Cebu province's cities and municipalities following integrated and holistic undertakings designed to respond to a wide range of problems (Alvarez, Ong and Abocejo, 2017), issues (Fernandez and Abocejo, 2014; Dela Serna, Ferrer and Abocejo, 2017) and local concerns (Abocejo and Gubalane, 2013). In 2008, the Cebu provincial government forged a partnership agreement with the Ramon Aboitiz Foundation Inc. (RAFI) for the implementation of the NAGa Programme under the Cebu provincial banner "*Our Cebu*" Programme (Ouano, 2013).

Before adoption of the NAGa programme it was evident that the local economy was undergoing slow pace of economic growth (Abocejo, 2017) punctuated by weak political leadership (Abocejo, 2015b) and loose coordination among elected officials belonging to different political parties (Evangelio and Abocejo, 2015). Issues on employees' tardiness and absenteeism, non-performing workers and low productivity were evident. Upon the introduction of the NAGa programme, public participation was essentially improved and intensified. Naga City village officials became active and participative most especially in decision-making.

The implementation of the NAGa Programme is two-fold. First, local government-based-the existing projects, interventions and activities of the departments and offices of the City Government are lodged at appropriate programme components of the NAGa Programme. The scorecard served as a guide in determining as to whether these are aligned to the standards for liveable, inclusive and competitive city. Second, village-based-the villages are very important implementing units of the NAGa Programme since in principle, the development on the ground always stems from the village. They are the front liners in programme implementation. Under the Programme, the villages are provided the framework to put village governance at work. Initially, they will participate in the NAGa Programme in the areas of cleanliness, sanitation and

health, greening, protection and enhancement of the environment, creativity and aesthetic impact, nurturance of the culture and heritage, and governance systems and structures.

The NAGa Programme is considered an important avenue in the delivery of basic services to Naga city constituents (Aboejo, 2015a; Vivar, Salvador and Aboejo, 2015). Just within three years of implementation (at the time of the study), the NAGa Programme (through its various executed projects) has created employment opportunities to local residents, helped and served the community. In cooperation with the Ramon Aboitiz Foundation, Inc. (RAFI), the Programme also extended and strengthened the government system of Naga City.

This study argues that the NAGa programme contributed to the economic development and good governance systems of the City of Naga, Cebu, Philippines. The various executed projects and activities facilitated the realisation of pro-active community-based cooperation, generating local employment prospects, re-invigorated the local economy with improved productivity and growth.

1.1 Study Objectives

This study evaluated the implementation of NAGa Programme in view of its status, challenges and successes. Specifically the study (1) determined status of programme implementation based on cleanliness, sanitation, health, governance systems and structures; (2) assessed the challenges and successes of programme implementation; and (3) evaluated how the programme contributes to city development in view of cleanliness, sanitation and health; governance, systems and structures.

1.2 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The study anchored its framework on the New Public Service Theory advocated by Denhardt and Denhardt (2000) which argues that public servants have the primary role of helping citizens and the people under their jurisdiction to meet their shared interest instead of attempting to control or manage their constituents. It focuses on the mission of the government which calls for collective public interests where considerations have to come before cost and efficiency and where citizens' participations are viewed as a major contributory factor in any public decision. Denhardt and Denhardt (2000) stressed further that the role of the administrator is very complex which includes synthesising the needs of citizens, interest groups, elected representatives, among others.

The "*Our Cebu Programme*" was institutionalised through Cebu Provincial Ordinance No. 2013-03. The ordinance mandates towards building sustainable cities and municipalities by promoting and encouraging LGUs and the private sector to engage in sustainable development initiatives. This Ordinance obliged LGUs to institute mechanisms for integrating the seven dimensions of sustainable development: namely; "*spiritual, human, social, cultural, political, economic and ecological*" thereby achieve progressive and self-reliant communities.

Figure 1: Theoretical and Conceptual Framework of the Study

Evidently, the NAGa Programme echoes the good governance paradigm in the context of Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs). The City of Naga, as one of the cities, entered into agreement with RAFI and put into effect strong collaboration with the private sector. Such action was concretised with the city’s sustainable development initiatives through the NAGa Programme. Among these projects were the Balik Siyudad, Adopt-a Village (or Purok), micro, small and medium enterprises, among others.

2. Research Methodology

The study employed a survey research design using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. It was implemented in the City of Naga which carried out the NAGa Programme following the standards and criteria through a balance scorecard. Programme assessment was undertaken in view of challenges and successes.

We employed interview questionnaires which focused in deriving information relevant to the administration of city and village officials in the NAGa Programme implementation. The questions were validated by experts in the discipline including the Head Specialist of the NAGa programme. There were two sets of these guide questions which is the first set is directed to the LGU officials and NAGa Programme team. The other set was directed to the village officials from the five most active and participative village and five from the least participative village based on their current status identified by the Chairman/Specialist of the Programme.

In cases where a substantial information were overlooked, vis-à-vis personal experiences, follow-up questions were set-up in open-ended form, this largely comprised the qualitative component of this study. Before conducting the interviews, a formal letter was forwarded to the Office of City Mayor and presented to the village officials for consent and approval.

Duly signed official request letters were sent to the local government of City of Naga seeking approval prior to the conduct of the study. The letter was officially

addressed to the Office of the City Mayor. Upon approval, similar letters were sent to the heads of the different departments of the City Government of Naga. Moreover, informed consent was secured from the key informants (KIs) where it was needed. Only after approval where dates for the conduct of were scheduled with the different village officials as KIs were set. All the primary and secondary generated data were keep with utmost confidentiality and were solely used for the purpose of the study.

The key informants included the NAGa Programme team which is composed of chairperson from different departments who passed the following inclusion criteria: City Health Office (CHO), City Veterinarian Office (Cvet), City Environment and Natural Resources Office (CENRO), City Nutrition Office (CNO), City Population Department Office (CPDO), City Local Government Office (CLGO), City Social Welfare and Development (CSWD), EA for Special Programmes and Projects and the Vice-Chairman. Village Officials from selected Village who adopted and implemented the Programme.

The KIs were drawn through purposive sampling which pre-selects them according to the needs of the study and whose positions in the City government of Naga are considered to be well conversant and who could provide the needed data to answer the stated problems of the study. Ten Villages were chosen and were divided into five most active and less active villages with respect to the NAGa programme implementation.

3. Results and Discussion

To attain the NAGa Programme targets, dynamic strategies were employed to bring ahead the initiatives of the City Government. These strategies were anchored on the principles of cooperation, ownership and accountability where all implementing units, i.e. LGU departments, villages and partners were involved in the different levels of programme implementation, monitoring and management.

3.1 The Scorecard System, Monitoring and Assessment

A scorecard system for the NAGa Programme was put in place. The system was intended to guide the local government implementing units achieve the Programme goals and objectives. Moreover, the scorecards serve as guide for the implementing units and the City constituency in general to view city development in an integrated, holistic and comprehensive manner. The scorecards also served as the management tool of department heads and village chieftains in running their respective offices and villages. They indicate the strengths and areas for improvement. The scorecards were instrumental as guide to address weak areas and to provide immediate courses of actions.

At the village level, a customised scorecard, dubbed as the Village Governance Scorecard, was formulated to tailor-fit the village situation. Other significant criteria and indicators were incorporated in the scorecard on a periodic basis to upgrade the

standards and raise the bars for village development. The scorecards are used in the entire process for monitoring and assessment.

A monitoring and assessment process is established to improve relevance and performance, or lack thereof, in the achievement of programme objectives. Feed backing of monitoring and assessment results from field monitoring visits to departments and villages is done in two ways. (1) Results are given to individual departments and village once every quarter through their Performance Scorecards, and (2) A report that is presented at the preceding month of the quarter during LGU Management Committee meetings. In the case of the villages, this is presented at the preceding month of the quarter, during regular meetings of the Association of Village [Barangay in local term] Captains (ABC).

The monitoring and assessment of the LGU departments is facilitated by both the Programme Management Team and the Technical Secretariat while that of the villages is done by the Technical Secretariat. There is an established guidelines and protocols for monitoring and assessment.

3.2 Recognition, Incentives and Awards Received

The City Government of Naga acknowledges and recognises the departments, offices and villages which show ingenuity and outstanding performance under the NAGa programme implementation. This was initiated to inspire and motivate the departments/offices and villages towards becoming pro-active partners of the City Government along the development process.

The standards and performance indicators as found in the programme scorecards are used as basis to determine the winners of NAGa Awards lodged under the City Government's annual Charter Day Celebration in September of each year. Guidelines and categories for the Awards are formulated to ensure the integrity and maintain credibility of the NAGa awards.

In relation to the banner of "*Our Cebu Programme*" From a mere 36th ranked local government in 2013, the City of Naga rose to 19th the following year, a giant leap as it garnered the third highest ranking spot for its 2015 overall performance under the *Our Cebu Programme*. The city of Naga made it to the top three and earned the distinction as an "*Exemplary LGU*" in the implementation of the "*Our Cebu Programme*". It bested five other component cities in the province of Cebu. For its outstanding feat, the City Government received a plaque of recognition and a check worth half a million pesos (roughly US 9,000 dollars) on 29 December 2015. The award proved local city government's commitment in the implementation of the NAGa Programme under its mother "*Our Cebu Program*".

3.3 Information Dissemination, Education Campaign and Programme Sustainability

To be able to implement the programme efficiently and effectively, the objectives, strategies and approaches of the programme should be thoroughly understood by all employees (across departments, offices and employment status) and villages. This also

allows them to see the bigger picture and understand their roles and responsibilities in the Programme and local governance in a broader context. Orientation workshops are facilitated for all implementing units while bill/bulletin boards, posters, among others are used as channels to get the message across and report programme status, accomplishments and milestones to the City of Naga constituency.

3.4 Programme Management and Administration

The City Government of Naga takes the active lead role of motivating shared responsibilities as well as initiate moves to mobilise, expand and integrate actions and efforts among departments, offices and villages for collaborative programme inventions.

The Naga City local government unit champions the NAGa Programme with the departments of the LGU and 28 villages and provide the legal mandate or authority for the departments and villages to undertake environment and socio-economic interventions as well as allocate resources and assets towards these interventions. A Programme Management Team (PMT) is installed to provide the leadership, management and oversight in order to ensure the effective implementation and sustainability of the NAGa Programme. The PMT serves as the principal steering group for the Programme and facilitates the effective management of inter-departmental (or inter-office) linkages and cross functional mechanisms to promote coordinated programme implementation and unified success.

The Technical Secretariat provides the PMT with timely, adequate, relevant and efficient administrative and technical assistance support in the management of the Programme. It is responsible for the execution of projects and activities as directed by the PMT. The technical Secretariat drums up the operations of the Programme and ensure these are enhanced and maintained.

3.5 Programme Sustainability

To ensure programme sustainability, the NAGa Programme, lobbies with the City Council for the passage of an ordinance to institutionalise programme standards, strategies and systems and mainstreamed at the LGU department and village levels. Since the various LGU departments and offices as well as the 28 villages of the City are seen as vital implementing units of the programme, they will undergo orientation workshops and basic seminars to ensure that programme interventions and objectives are thoroughly understood and adopted.

Further, the local city government gives emphasis and strengthens collaboration with the private sector and draws its active participation in the city's sustainable development process through the NAGa Programme. This shall include approach in "*Balik Siyudad*", Adopt-a village (or suburbs) and organise local councils for micro, small and medium enterprises who shall set up the systems and enabling environment for small and micro-entrepreneurs in the City.

3.6 Status of the Implementation of the NAGa Programme

The “Naga Akong Garbo” (NAGa) programme has its mother programme from the “Our Cebu Program” of the provincial government of Cebu. After years of implementation of the NAGa programme (and still ongoing), it becomes imperative to assess the status of its implementation, how far it has achieved the goals and targets. The table below shows the perceived extent of implementation of the NAGa programme based on five major indicators assessed in this study.

Table 1: Status of implementation of the NAGa programme

Criterion	Mean	SD	Description
Cleanliness	3.90	0.85	Implemented enough
Sanitation	3.55	0.69	Implemented enough
Health	3.85	0.81	Implemented enough
Governance systems	4.10	0.72	Implemented enough
Governance structures	4.35	0.67	Highly Implemented
Grand Mean	3.95		Implemented enough
Overall SD		0.78	
Ranges for the Weighted Mean Description			
1.00 -	1.80	Not Implemented	
1.81 -	2.60	Slightly implemented	
2.61 -	3.40	Moderately implemented	
3.41 -	4.20	Implemented enough	
4.21 -	5.00	Highly implemented	

As a whole, the NAGa programme has been implemented enough (Table 1). The same holds true for all indicators except on the governance structures where it is viewed as highly implemented by the KIs. Notably, there is positive and favourable observations about programme’s implementation with regard to cleanliness, sanitation, health, and governance systems. This confirms what many KIs described that the NAGa programme has been achieving its goals in line with the policy statement of “Our Sustainable Cebu Programme”, as its mother programme.

For instances, in the implementation of the NAGa cleanliness initiative, it was confirmed by the KIs that “all villages have fully implemented the programme in partnership with the DOH and with full participation of each Village’s Health Workers (BHWs). Each Village is provided with a regular visit of private Doctors who serves once and twice a week” (L16-19). In this regard, the cleanliness subcomponent of the NAGa programme has been implemented enough. This also holds true for the sanitation and health component of the NAGa programme.

The consistency of ratings given by the 20 KIs for each of the cleanliness, sanitation, health and governance systems indicators are notable in the standard deviation (SD) values which are small at 0.85, 0.69, 0.81 and 0.72, in that order. The smaller SD values reflect that all KIs have evaluation ratings close to the corresponding mean in each indicator. In other words, all of their ratings are in close agreement that cleanliness, sanitation, health and governance systems are implemented enough. There is an apparent concordance among the KIs (based on SD values) in their views about

the extent of implementation of NAGa programme on cleanliness, sanitation, health and governance systems. Meanwhile, the governance structures happened to be the lowest among all indicators' SD at 0.67 which suggests firmer concordance of being highly implemented as viewed by all KIs.

With respect to the governance systems, the NAGa programme is viewed to be implemented enough. This indicates satisfactory accomplishment of the programme as manifested on the *"improved governance in each village where the best programme implementer is recognised and awarded. Good governance mirrors what kind of village Officials a village has"* (L71-74). With the implementation of the programme, *"each village has become more knowledgeable and aware on pertinent implemented projects in their area like the provision of financial assistance to solo parents"* (L74-76). *The programme has brought wider spectrum of awareness to the people in each village most especially those who are in the mountainous area to become more educated about solo parenting and inherent legalities"* (L77-79).

As a manifestation of its highly implemented governance structures, the city of Naga has been showing success in its NAGa programme which *"helps the City government to improve public service deliveries which serve as yardstick for the quality services to its constituents. Another positive aspect is the favourable response from the people of Naga to the programme"* (L203-206). This is manifested by the *"Supportive community which makes the delivery of public service efficient and effective"* (L187-188). In fact, the *"NAGa was awarded with the seal of Good Governance and this goes to show that all the administration, city officials, city office heads, village officials are working harmoniously"* (L190-192). This further confirms the fact that there is *"cooperation among the various group of individuals from the office down to the Village and Sitio Level."* (L254-255). Evidently, there is *"Increase levels of awareness which boosts people's confidence to help and recreate a strong Nagahanons"* (L194-195). In its entirety, effective implementation of governance structures takes place when there is *"full support from the administration"* (L234). This is proven by the Naga *"city government which gives its full support to the programme with passion and commitment"* (L244-245).

3.7 Challenges and Successes in the Implementation of NAGa programme

Amidst the ongoing implementation of the NAGa programme by all stakeholders, it is always confronted with some challenges. As confirmed by the KIs, that there's a *"hard time in accomplishing paper works relevant to the programme like documentations, pictures, minutes of the meetings, attendance, etc."* (L132-134). Some notable challenges include highly technical entries in the scorecard whose indicators are not easy to comprehend among the village level programme implementers. Some of the participating villages are also less responsive cast shadowed by vested political interests. Another major challenge is delayed releases of budget for project NAGa related project implementation. These are outlined in Table 2.

Other KIs also observed that the *"scorecards create pressure to do the work in its timely and overloaded paper work"* (L167). *"It gives more additional paper works for compliance*

to the scorecard and standards given” (L135) need in completing and meeting their set standard. Many KIs agreed that the scorecards have high standard set in every indicator putting them in difficulty achieving such standard scores. For them these set standards pose greater challenge in responding to the desired accomplishment of the NAGa programme.

On the positive note, there are already visible successes achieved in the implementation of the NAGa Programme. These include the positive results which are yielded in spite the challenges the come along with the implementation initiatives. Foremost is the affirmation from the KIs that the programme has *“empowered the Village Officials to work more and enhance the delivery of services rendered for the whole community. Projects are also introduce and it creates teamwork which leads into a strong and united people”* (L347-349). Certainly one of the KI’s shared his view *“that everyone in the community has become more willing to cooperate, developed good relationship with the stakeholders like the GO Transparent, CEMEX Quarry Venture Philippines Incorporated”* (L350-351). The NAGa programme guided each official to improve public service and community linkages via the stakeholders and their constituents making and realising the projects implemented by the LGU efficiently and effectively.

The programme as examined by the KIs, *“guides the village Officials in their duties and responsibilities”* (L359-360). Due to the provision of the Cebu Provincial Ordinance, they become responsive to do the tasks in fulfilling their works as public servants. Though sudden changes are often difficult to achieve, the programme still able to help each village to improve the life and standard of living of the community. Other KI’s reported that *“specific projects gradually solve problems in the village. Officials are able to improve their quality of rendered services to the people. Public services become more efficient”* (L353-355). This clearly shows that the programme through the conduct of meetings for follow-up, sessions, seminars and trainings, serves as a key eye-opener to the City and Village Officials of the City of Naga. *“The village has concretely achieved development far better than prior before the NAGa Programme adoption. This gives hope for the local residents to see changes but only if everyone embraces it wholeheartedly”* (L356-358).

Table 2: Challenges and successes in the implementation of NAGa programme

Challenges	Successes
<p>Highly technical indicators of the scorecards.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to understand documents to fill up for reports. • <i>“Take a longer time in educating the people and change their perception towards the programme”</i> (L125). • <i>“Lack and availability of people to handle specific task”</i> (L171). • <i>“Difficulty in monitoring because of too many indicators to be followed”</i> (L278). • <i>“No documents are shown every time the LGU conducts the evaluation, no points will be given for the specific area”</i> (L328-329). 	<p>The programme substantially improved public service delivery to the community.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“The programme serves as guide for village officials”</i> (L222 and L354) • <i>“like projects are introduced”</i> (L344) • <i>“Visitations for operation Tuli and Special Immunisation for Kids”</i> (L70-71). • <i>“Anti-rabies treatment/project help people to have a quick access on it compared last year.”</i> (L88 and L199). • <i>“Health programmes are created and just recently the Animal-bite Centre”</i> (L211). • <i>“Strengthened prohibited drugs monitoring and</i>

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	<p><i>police system to provide protection for individuals” (L358).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Each Village put up Village Animal Health Aid (BAHA), a person who guides the medical team in their visitation”(L82-83).</i>
<p>Some village officials are unresponsive due to political vested interests.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Different political party which creates barrier for the success of any programme implemented in the Village Level.” (L369-370)</i> 	<p>Improved relationship among various programme departments, stakeholders and the community.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Coordinate with other offices like Mayor’s Office, PNP-DILG” (L52).</i> • <i>“if run out of funds, their supervisors will look for ways to tap stakeholders to realise a specific project” (L56-57).</i>
<p>Slow budget releases cause delay the implementation of projects.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>“Seminars are sometimes delayed and not implemented due to lack of budget and funds or slow process in releasing the budget.” (L122-123)</i> • Some village become less active due to budget delays. • Entrepreneurship, business and livelihood programmes and projects are not attain (based on scorecard data) 	<p>Garnered achievements and commendations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has improved ranking from the first year of programme implementation to present, from 36th rank in 2013, from 19th rank in 2014 to 3rd rank in 2015. • Received plaque of certificate as “Exemplary LGU” • 2015 Child-friendly Local Governance Award • <i>“Awards like Seal of Good House Keeping”, making the people work at its best potential with honesty and integrity” (L181-182).</i> • The village chairman received a plaque of recognition for being one of the nominees to The Outstanding Village Officials of the Year (TOBOY) for 2014.

Another milestone success of the NAGa programme can be gleaned from its mere 36th rank LGU way back in 2013, then it rose to 19th rank a year after. The City of Naga made a giant leap as it grabbed the third highest ranking spot for its 2015 overall performance in the “Our Cebu Programme”. This Industrial City of Cebu South made it to the top three and earned the distinction as an “Exemplary LGU” in the implementation of the Our Cebu Programme, besting five other component cities in Cebu. For its outstanding feat, the City Government received a plaque of recognition and a check worth half a million pesos during the awarding rites at the Provincial Capitol Social Hall last December 29, 2015 The award is a concrete manifestation of the City Government of Naga’s commitment to pursue and implement the Our Cebu Programme through the NAGa (RAFI, 2016).

The City Government of Naga takes the active lead role of motivating shared responsibilities as well as initiate moves to mobilise, expand and integrate actions and efforts among departments, offices and villages for collaborative programme inventions. The City Government champions the NAGa Programme with the departments of the LGU and 28 villages and provides the legal mandate or authority for the departments and villages to undertake environment and socio-economic interventions as well as allocate resources and assets towards these interventions.

3.8 Contributions of the NAGa programme to the development of the city of Naga

The City Government of Naga acknowledges and recognises the departments, offices and villages which show ingenuity and outstanding performance in programme implementation. This intends to inspire and motivate the departments/offices and villages to take that gigantic move towards being an active partner of the City Government in its development process. The standards and performance indicators as found in the programme scorecards are used as basis to determine the winners of the NAGa Awards lodged under the City Government’s annual Charter Day Celebration in September of each year. The following table shows the ratings on cleanliness, sanitation and health.

It should be noted that the new scorecard already contains different indicators when compared with the previous one. The Cebu Province, where the mother “*Our Cebu Programme*” emanates, periodically changes and improve the scorecard wherein new relevant indicators for monitoring and performance are added. The previous version has fewer indicators which are much simpler, whereas the recent one has more stringent indicators being adopted for the present evaluation of NAGa programme performance. Evidently, the recent village-scorecard contains many specific strands where points to be given are distributed accordingly. Operationally, the revisions of the scorecard has led to more specific but improved criteria like those applied and used for cleanliness, sanitation and health, governance systems and structures.

Table 3: Rating for “*cleanliness, sanitation and health*” and governance systems and structures

Criterion	Score Card Standard Rating	Mean based on Score Card	Percent Rating to Standard (%)
Cleanliness, Sanitation and Health	0.301	0.291	96.68
Governance Systems and Structures	0.17	0.16	94.12

Table 3 shows the scorecard ratings, means based on scorecard and corresponding ratings to standard in percent. The figures were derived from the core indicators used by the NAGa programme in evaluating its village level performance as rated by the Programme Management Team (PMT). The desired scores is to reach 100 percent performance as can be gleaned from the table, where cleanliness, sanitation and health attained 96.68 percent rating while governance systems and structures posted a rating of 94.12 percent.

In general, the main based scores reflect that the NAGa programme implementation, viewed from the two assessed criteria, has achieved commendable performance. It is worth noting that several core indicators were considered and used in the scoring criteria. Operationally, to arrive at the mean based score which, came out very close to the standard rating, implies that nearly all core indicators were rated at the same level with the score card standard. This performance is confirmed with the various awards and commendations that the Naga City LGU has been conferred in recent years, most notably when it was recognised as an Exemplary LGU. The City of

Naga has demonstrated concrete improvements in the delivery of various services under the two assessed criteria in particular.

Visibly, *"the programme has extended City of Naga government's arm in serving and protecting everyone"* (L201-202). *"Over the past years, some health workers were easy-go-lucky, lax of their work and sometimes absent. But due to the strict implementation and monitoring from the administration, everything has changed"* (Line183-185). *"When the programme started, many opportunities were newly open to accommodate public and private individual"* (L197-198). *"The NAGa programme helps the City Health Workers to improve in public service"* (L215). *"Each Village put up BAHA –Village Animal Health Aid, a person who guides the Medical Team in their visitation. It becomes a major contribution since it make their delivery of public service efficient"* (L82-84). *"Anti-Rabies treatment helps people to have a quick access on it compared last year"* (L199-200).

With respect to governance systems and structures, *"for some, the NAGa programme serves as their guide to know the real essence of being Village Officials"* (L222-223). *"The NAGa programme helps the City government to improve in public service because it serves as yardstick or tool for the quality service direct to the people"* (L203-204). *"The programme also serves as their key and someday would benefit the city's development as well as to future sons and daughters"* (L228-229). *"Improvement in each Village is evident like making the Village and the Nagahanon being active, so far in all implemented projects of NAGa programme"* (L230-231). Ultimately, *"if people will be guided, most probably the goal for sustainability and long-term development will be attained"* (L227-228).

However, comparing the perceptions of KIs (Table 1) and the percent rating to standard (Table 3) yield some divergent results. The KIs perceived cleanliness, sanitation and health to be implemented enough while the percent rating for the combined of this criteria did not reached 100 percent as desired. This can be due to the fact that the rating scales used are different; the former utilised a 4-scale likert scale measure where the latter is based 100 percentage point. Secondly, the Table 1 reflects perception levels while Table 3 displays mean aggregate value from actual scores generated from the field levels. The same pattern is observable for the governance systems and structures, the criteria have been perceived to be highly implemented (Table 1) although it has not also attained the 100 percent desired rating of 100 percent (Table 3).

According to the village level KIs that whenever *"no document is shown every time the LGU conducts the evaluation, no point is given for a specific criteria"* (L328-329). This leads to some villages get no point hindering them from meeting the required rating. In like manners, the City Government of Naga KIs revealed that the *"CHO depends primarily on the health status report from each village, if no report given, no assistance can be given"* (L148-150). City official KIs also noted that in terms of governance systems and structures, *"all Villages have implemented the programme, however Village officials lack the initiatives in implementing and facilitating programmes with their constituents"* (L12-13). Records from the PMT show that *"creating livelihood Programmes for the unemployed"* is one of the areas that need to be improved and be strengthened.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

In the light of the findings of the study, it is concluded that the Naga Akong Garbo (NAGa) Programme has been implemented enough in view of its cleanliness, sanitation, health and governance systems while highly implemented with respect to governance structures. The study confirms the arguments of the New Public Service Theory in view of the Naga City local leaders who strive to responsively serve their constituents for community-based growth and development.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby put forward in view of improving further the NAGa programme. To overcome the challenges, there is a need to lessen paper works (processing and reporting), improve onsite visitation, strengthen info dissemination about programme benefit and encourage more active community involvement. To sustain success—continue trainings, seminar workshops, enhance programme standard based on scorecard. Active participation in the formulation and implementation of projects, programmes and policies of the village. Conduct related studies considering to all the components of the NAGa Programme.

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STATUS, CHALLENGES AND SUCCESSES

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